

PL059

AirHealth SWS Platforms

End of Project Report

This report is intended to be published and made available via the project's webpage on the ARDC website (certain sections can be redacted if requested). Please write this report for an audience who are not already familiar with this project.

Project Information

1. Project Details:

Project title: "Scientific workflow system for environmental health impact assessments"

<https://doi.org/10.47486/PL059>

Lead organisation: The University of Sydney

Other organisations involved in project: Curtin University, The Centre for Air pollution, energy and health Research (CAR), Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN), University of Queensland, NSW Department of Planning, Industry and Environment, Environment Protection Authority Victoria, Monash University and NSW Health.

Contact person name: Dr Ivan Hanigan

Reporting period: December 9, 2021 to June 20, 2022

2. Background

During the previous reporting period (2021) the project was conducted according to the project plan with most work completed at the University of Sydney. In contrast, during this reporting period (since January 2022) Dr Ivan Hanigan, the lead of the Air-Health-SWS Platforms project, moved from The University of Sydney to Curtin University. This change in the project team structure was beneficial because Dr Hanigan's new role as the Director of the WHO Collaborating Centre for Environmental Health Impact Assessment at Curtin University is closely aligned with all of the aims and objectives of the project. However, there were some associated contractual issues and the working arrangements had to be modified and a sub-contract with Curtin University created. The University of Sydney remained the lead organisation and Associate Professor Geoff Morgan took on the administration and project governance. At Curtin University, Dr

Hanigan committed to completing the deliverables as per the project plan and support the ongoing work of the related project ARDC PS022 Public Sector Research Bridges “Air-Health-Data”.

3. Achievement of project aims:

Please note that this project is linked with the ARDC funded “Air Health Data National Data Asset” project (<https://doi.org/10.47486/PS022>) and forms an underlying supporting platform of software development and infrastructure provision for the work undertaken in that related ARDC project.

These two projects work in tandem to create harmonised and integrated air pollution and health datasets that will help inform policy makers, epidemiologists, and public sector agencies.

1. This Platforms project was designed to deliver a scientific workflow system (SWS) for health impact assessments (HIAs) that can be used widely by environmental agencies and industrial organisations to consider the health burden of their policies and activities. Stakeholder and end user engagement is crucial for alignment of SWS capabilities broadly, and to ensure fitness for specific industry and government policy needs. The work packages lead to a standardised computational approach, with alertness to the discourse concerning epidemiological assumptions and limitations.
2. With an advisory network of stakeholders and scientific collaborators, the design of software architecture for a production quality system forms the key deliverables of this project. Also considering the raft of possible technologies, such as Apache Airflow, R Shiny, Snakemake and R targets, and previously developed tool’s, such as the US EPA Environmental Benefits Mapping and Analysis Program (BenMAP; <https://www.epa.gov/benmap>), the SWS framework requires versatility and a common denominator approach to managing and scheduling computational modules.
3. The third aspect for this project is an accumulation of R functions and scripts that have been designed around specific use cases. These coerce the architecture towards the varied requirements of the stakeholders, and into a form that enhances the capability of existing technical and interfacing resources in stakeholder agencies.
4. The final phase involves supporting the ARDC “Air-Health Bridges” project and subsequently the tracking of users, their publications, grants and reports, and policy information for which the tools have been developed. In 2021, the foundations for future impacts were laid through stakeholder workshops, canvassing and engagement of a broader user base. Having established user needs and consolidated the SWS capabilities, this deliverable is achieved through a simple procedure for accessing the data on CARDAT and using the SWS, which prompts users for their Cloudstor credentials and then downloads necessary data from the CARDAT database. Logins are recorded to enable outcomes tracking and reporting.

4. Achievements against project work packages:

Record achievement of project work packages, including details of the deliverables, in the table below **or in a spreadsheet** if preferred.

Use the following criteria and colours to assign a status to each work package:

Status Key

Non-completion has no impact on outcome	Not yet completed, however, has no impact on project outcomes. Responsibility for completion has been assigned and agreed by the Steering Committee.
Non-completion has some impact on project outcomes	Not yet completed and non-completion may have some impact on the project outcomes. Delay has been accepted by the Steering Committee and responsibility for completion has been assigned.
Will not be completed and has impact on project outcomes	Will not be completed and has an impact on the project outcomes. The Steering Committee has accepted the non-completion and understands the impact to the project outcomes.
Completed	Completed.

Milestone / Deliverable / Work Package	Details of progress including explanation of any variation (include links to relevant documentation)	Agreed Due Date	Actual Completion Date or Expected Completion Date	Status (highlight colour as per table above)
WP1	<p>Coordinate advice from academic and policy stakeholders to define HIA scenarios and epidemiological methods.</p> <p>We held the first steering committee meeting on May 31st 2021 and had complete attendance from our stakeholders. The meeting broadly identified priority capabilities and characteristics of the SWS. Subsequently, we met individually with all of the stakeholders and identified other users from several state and local government agencies, including the Inner West council and Sutherland shire council.</p> <p>From the user priorities listed in the previous PL059 project report (09/12/2021), it became clear that the SWS for calculating mortality burden of air pollution could serve all interests by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. accommodating user-provided pollutant surfaces 2. enabling users to generate counterfactual scenarios based on hypothetical changes in air pollution exposures 3. providing HIA modules for acute exposures (such as heatwaves and bushfires smoke plumes) with mortality data at small temporal scales. 	09/12/2021	09/12/2021	Complete

<p>WP2</p>	<p>Build prototype systems</p> <p>As outlined in the PL059 project report submitted in December 2021, we explored multiple approaches to the development of the SWS. Among these, a deployable workflow infrastructure can be viewed at https://github.com/cardat/air-health-sws-airflow. This Apache Airflow tool was produced through engagement with the Sydney Informatics Hub (SIH) and software developer training in consultation with experts from multiple industry, government and academic organisations. The product of this work is public: https://github.com/cardat/air-health-sws-airflow.</p> <p>Also outlined in the previous project report the AirFlow tool used an R based scripted workflow which at that time incorporated mortality data at temporal and spatial levels not previously available. This package performs HIAs of PM2.5 and NO2 surfaces from multiple air pollution models developed at UQ, the CSIRO, EPA Vic and NSW DPE.</p> <p>During 2022, continued collaboration with stakeholders at NSW DPE and EPA Vic led to refined conceptions of end user requirements, in particular with the recognition of considerable technical and interfacing capacity in those institutions, where web portals and interactive desktops with mapping capabilities are supported using open source R shiny and R Leaflet packages and the Microsoft product power BI. Air-health SWS needs to be easily incorporated at the back end of interfaces that are designed and built by our stakeholder agencies. Therefore, we investigated the R targets package for its compatibility with R shiny and its capacity to empower our data analysis tools. The R-targets format functionalises R scripted HIA steps to provide persistence of user storage and background processes, to avoid computationally demanding steps that needn't be updated, to speed up iteration and to ease the burden of code development for future use cases.</p> <p>The product of our development using R-targets can be accessed at https://github.com/cardat/air-health-sws-r-targets, where a simple step by step user guide can be found with three case studies that meet the research infrastructure (RI) priorities identified during 2021.</p>	<p>09/12/2021</p>	<p>09/12/2021</p>	<p>Complete</p>
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<p>WP3</p>	<p>Expand the repertoire of computational capabilities of the SWS</p> <p>At the time of our last project report, we had developed a package of R scripts that together source population, mortality and exposure data and resolve spatial and temporal parameters to estimate attributable deaths and years of life lost. These had also been configured in an instance of Apache Airflow on a Nectar Cloud allocation of TERN.</p> <p>As described for WPs 1 and 2, continuous stakeholder consultations led us to operationalise the SWS using R targets, and we presented the resulting tools on June 9th 2022 at our ARDC workshop entitled "Integrated national air pollution and health data". Please see the presentation video at this link: https://cloudstor.aarnet.edu.au/plus/s/waCHnARPrN5cgP8.</p> <p>The R targets SWS can be used with any user-provided air pollution surface (raster file) for PM2.5 and/or NO2 and can be used to model counterfactual scenarios by imposing hypothetical pollution cessation amounts on the current identified air pollution dataset held on the CARDAT system. As demonstrated by the 3 case studies (https://github.com/cardat/air-health-sws-r-targets), the R targets SWS offers a repertoire of applications in a format that is ready for integration into a variety of interfacing modalities.</p> <p>At the recent major workshop for the Bridges project (held June 9th 2022) the SWS was demonstrated with the intention of drawing out further applications and communicating specific requests for mortality data in novel configurations of time and space. Notably, in addition to monthly deaths data at statistical area 4 (SA4), greater capital city (GCC) and local government area (LGA) levels stratified into 7 age bands for all years between 2000 and 2019, the project team were in unanimous agreement that daily numbers of deaths at the GCC level would be a great asset. Hence, the SWS will be coerced again into a form that calculates numbers of deaths that can be attributed to short term exposures to high levels of air pollution under the related ARDC PS022 Public sector bridges project plan. To produce high quality exposure data for studies of bushfire smoke plumes and other short lived air pollution events, we engaged with the Australian Space Data Analysis Facility (ASDAF) and added a bushfire smoke data sharing tool which we also use for hosting extreme weather data (including high fire-danger weather parameters). Please see https://github.com/cardat/air-health-bushfire-smoke-netcdf</p>	<p>20/06/2022</p>	<p>24/06/2022</p>	<p>Complete</p>
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<p>WP4</p>	<p>Outcomes and impacts reporting</p> <p>As mentioned above for WP1, we ran a campaign of stakeholder engagement to entice users from all state and territory environmental agencies and several local government councils.</p> <p>To improve visibility of the RI, we demonstrated its use at a Centre for Air pollution, health and energy Research workshop on Dec 8, 2021 and an ARDC workshop on June 9th, 2022 (video is at https://cloudstor.aarnet.edu.au/plus/s/waCHnARPrN5cqP8). By aligning closely with the user priorities from WP1, the R-targets SWS is an immediate source of policy relevant information for environmental agencies and local governments. Like the US EPA tool BenMAP, the workflow system uses WHO recommended methods and risk estimates for mortality and Australian spatial, population, health and air pollution exposure data, which have been consolidated on the platform CARDAT under the Bridges project PS022. Unlike BenMAP, however, the SWS is not prescriptive of the user interfaces that it will enhance. The R-targets functions that have been developed herein during 2022 can be called sequentially and coordinated behind interactive desktop tools, such as R-shiny and R-Leaflet.</p> <p>As the associated Public Sector Bridges project PS022 continues to improve the spatiotemporal qualities of datasets, this RI will become Australia's best resource for determining health impacts of priority air pollution and other atmospheric hazards or policy interventions (e.g. climate change action).</p> <p>We are focused on these RI qualities because they will ensure future outcomes and impacts, which we will track and report in the coming years using information collected on our user registration proforma as part of the PS022 Bridges project. Please see https://doi.org/10.47486/PS022.</p> <p>This work package has therefore been transferred to the continuing PS022 project deliverables as follows: user tracking modules complete by 20 June 2023, final outcomes tracking report due 20 June 2025.</p>	<p>20/06/2022</p>	<p>20/06/2022</p>	<p>Complete</p>

If your project used Agile or/and Kanban Frameworks you can include snapshots from tools or summaries using one or all of the below:

- Product Release charts
- Sprint releases
- Output charts

5. Issues/Challenges

Please list **significant** issues or challenges encountered during project delivery, using the following table or [link to an Issues register](#).

Id.	Issue	Priority	Raised by	Date raised	Responsibility	Required resolution date	Progress & dates	Resolution	Status
	<p>AirFlow vs R-targets.</p> <p>When we completed WP1 (Define policy relevant HIAs with acquired datasets) and WP2 (Locally developed prototype Apache Airflow) and we moved to WP3 (SWS deployed on Nectar Cloud allocation of TERN CoESRA) we found that the available architecture on TERN COESRA (Kubernetes) did not align with our local prototype leading to challenges for our developer. We obtained a standalone VM on TERN CoESRA Nectar cloud but when deploying the service we met delays and so asked ARDC that the Milestone 4 (Approved final report) be delayed for 6 months until June 2022.</p> <p>When we went to develop Apache Airflow on TERN CoESRA Nectar cloud, unfortunately we found that Apache Airflow, while offering a platform for scheduling and prioritising workflow tasks, is not immediately suited to health impact assessment workflows. It is more suited to our other tasks such as frequent (hourly) ingress of new air monitor data.</p> <p>Meanwhile in parallel developments the capabilities of our R-based workflow have been expanded to accommodate the user priorities we identified in WP1. We pivoted slightly to use the R based SWS modules in the R-targets workflow system (https://github.com/ropensci/targets) and developed that as the best candidate for a backend to user</p>	High	van Hanigan	Thursday, December	van Hanigan	June 2022	Completed	Implement R-targets	Closed

<p>interfaces such as R-shiny, R-Leaflet and Power BI.</p> <p>We met with ARDC expert Jonathan Smillie to discuss the proposed R 'targets' & Airflow set up in more detail and decided to focus on the R-targets toolkit.</p>													
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6. Project Acceptance

Have all the original needs of the stakeholders been met, and are there any ongoing concerns that need to be documented and/or addressed?

This project was conceived through a series of consultations with agencies such as EPA Vic and NSW DPE, with whom cross sectoral relationships had been established on the basis of collaborative health impact assessments of air pollution. These agencies and our other stakeholders needed a validated scientific workflow system that could be adapted in house to perform priority health risk assessments of policy changes. The present R-Targets SWS meets these original needs and provides further capabilities, as identified during our consultative project development process.

The tools have not yet been integrated into stakeholder systems. Initially, some technical consultation will be available from our team, who continue to be employed under the Bridges project PS022 and await the opportunity to test the final product *in situ*.

7. Sustainability plans

Please indicate what plans have been put in place for continued operation of the platform, and how these will be supported.

The Air-Health SWS will now form an integral part of the ongoing Bridges Air-Health data repository and research infrastructure. The R-targets HIA tool will be tested further using real life policy questions and will be used to develop and refine machine to machine operability using the products of the machine readable metadata module of the PS022 project <https://doi.org/10.47486/PS022>.

Further sustainability of Air-Health SWS will be achieved under the national consortium Healthy Environments And Lives (HEAL) National Research Network, which received \$10M from the National Health and Medical Research Council (Grant No. 2008937). Under the Data and Decision Support Systems work package of the HEAL project, Dr Hanigan and a large number of science and policy stakeholders bear the responsibility of coordinating the development of nationally consistent environmental public health research infrastructure by consolidating existing platforms, such as AusEnHealth

<https://www.ausenhealth.com/home> and the tools being developed by the Population Interventions Unit at University of Melbourne <https://league-table.shinyapps.io/bode3/>.

Lessons learnt

8. What went well?

What positive lessons can be usefully applied to other projects? Did the ARDC support/partnership benefit the project’s outcomes?

- The project strengthened partnerships with TERN and ARDC support, in the form of cores, which will greatly improve the usability of Air-Health SWS on the Virtual Desktop services of COESRA.
- Our stakeholder consultations led to a comprehensive list of use cases, which were effectively distilled into targeted spatial and temporal parameterisations of the platform.

9. What could be improved?

Are there lessons learnt that can usefully be applied to other projects? i.e.

- Were risks identified early enough and were mitigation strategies effective?
- Were there any issues that could have been avoided? If so, how?
- Could any issues/risks be avoided for future projects?
- Were there any changes to the project as originally planned? If so, are there any reflections or considerations which could be considered for future similar projects?
- How can ARDC’s support/partnership improve to meet the project’s needs?

Description	Impact on project	What was actioned/could be a solution(s) for future projects
At the start of the project, we invested heavily in Apache Airflow as the software of choice for the SWS. It wasn’t until the end of 2021 that we pivoted to R-targets.	The money spent on software development could have been better spent on other work packages and R-targets developments. This impact was small though and the Airflow product will be invaluable as we develop infrastructure for bushfire smoke plume data ingest.	Advice from software experts who are employed at stakeholder institutions needs to be sought earlier and acted upon. Software development parts of the project need to be planned more carefully at the start of the project. It should be noted that recruitment of software engineering skills takes time. Optimally these skills would be held by team members at the start of the project.

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10. Anything else you would like to tell us about the project:

<Enter text here>

FAIR

11. FAIR Project Outputs

Describe how the **project** outputs (publications, documentation, code, etc) have been made FAIR, with particular focus on any reuse or potential for reuse of outputs beyond the original purpose.

We use the GitHub, Nectar, TERN and Cloudstor platforms to make the project outputs FAIR. For example:

- We adopted and adapted the Scientific Workflow System (SWS) known as R-targets to build a pipeline for environmental health impact assessment using air pollution as a case study. **The R-targets scientific workflow system code** and user guidelines are freely available on GitHub at: <https://github.com/cardat/air-health-sws-r-targets>
- We adopted and adapted the SWS called “Airflow” to facilitate automated processing of environmental health datasets in the Australian research cloud. The configured **AirFlow code and user guide is available as a github repo** (it is private now because it holds scripts that are IP protected) <https://github.com/cardat/air-health-sws-airflow>
- We worked with programmers at the Sydney Informatics Hub (SIH) extended relevant GIS tools from the open source Python, R and QGIS environments to augment tools from the proprietary software suite ESRI ArcGIS (TM) and our new **GIS tools code and user guide is available as a public github repo**: <https://github.com/cardat/air-health-gis-tools> . We recruited GIS analyst Ori Tarabulus employed at USydney to extend that work and his codes will be available on GitHub too (at the repository we started here https://github.com/cardat/air_health_gis_arcpy).
- We adopted and adapted the THREDDS application programming interface services to facilitate data sharing using the file format netCDF. This work will facilitate efficiently reading the data and taking spatio-temporal subsets (such as SA1 level averages. **The netCDF tools and user guide are available** on GitHub: <https://github.com/cardat/air-health-bushfire-smoke-netcdf> . For this work we recruited data scientist Dr Miles Sowden who created a tool (assisted with in-kind contributions of a programmer team from the Australian Space Data Analysis Facility (ASDAF) to embed machine readable metadata in netCDF. CAR’s data curator (Karthik Gopi) prepared the metadata on our CARDAT

data inventory and TERN set up of the API endpoint ready to host this at

<https://dap.tern.org.au/thredds/catalog/> “Historical_Extreme_Weather_Events_Australia”.

- Work has begun with ARDC expert Melanie Barlow to develop tool to attach machine-readable metadata using the Ecological Metadata Language EML (https://github.com/ivanhanigan/data_inventory/blob/master/static/R/datinv2eml.R)
- All datasets are accessible from the AARNET Cloudstor data sharing platform (<http://cloudstor.aarnet.edu.au/>).

12. Implementing FAIR Platforms

Describe how the Platform itself is FAIR, with particular focus on any reuse or potential for reuse of platform components beyond the original purpose (if this is not already described in Section 11).

- The R-based SWS now includes R-targets modules that protect privacy and provenance of data by deriving fit for purpose datasets for direct use in HIAs. In the case of mortality data, the derived HIA outputs conceal raw deaths data using calculated mortality rates in small areas. In this way, we ensure FAIR-readiness of spatially and temporally explicit mortality data that is otherwise available only through lengthy ethics application processes and costly data purchases.
- We acquired modelled air pollution data from Dr Luke Knibbs and derived estimates at the meshblock level. While the raw data are not available without permission, the SWS retrieves these high resolution data as inputs for HIAs with only need for authorised permission set on request to the CAR data curator.
- The SWS promises a standardised HIA approach that will facilitate comparisons between states and other jurisdictions through reproducible analyses.

13. Implementing FAIR-enabling Platforms

Describe what functions/features have been implemented in the Platform to enable FAIR outputs (i.e. how are data, code, visualisations, etc produced or processed by the Platform made FAIR/FAIRer).

- The scientific workflow system from the platforms project PL059 is ready for public use (available on GitHub and deployed on TERN CoESRA Virtual Desktops). It provides mediated access to

exposure and health datasets that are otherwise difficult to obtain, and in some cases are not available without extensive permissions and ethics procedures and even considerable cost. These privileged datasets can be accessed by our computational tools without disclosure, making the data FAIR.

- The platform itself offers a standardised method for health impact assessment (HIA), thus improving reproducibility of HIAs across the country.
- The SWS prompts users for their Cloudstor credentials and then downloads necessary data from the CARDAT database. Logins are recorded to enable outcomes tracking and reporting.

Project Impact

The Government wishes to demonstrate the impact on researchers (and industry and the general public) of the NCRIS investment, and the ARDC Board is particularly concerned with being able to demonstrate the value of the investment in Research Platforms.

ARDC realises that a number of possible impact metrics are lag indicators.

14. Platform impact metrics

Impact metric (*add relevant details/links in next section)	Progress report 1	Progress report 2	Progress report 3	Progress report 4
Number of datasets published (preferably with record in Research Data Australia)*		1. National Air Pollution Monitor Database (NAPMD), 2. CAR FireSmoke version 1.2, 3. daily mortality outcomes Sydney		
Number of publications using data generated by platform*		1. Heatwaves, UHI and mortality paper.		

Number of publications that cite /reference the platform*		2 papers cite the Bridges project which uses this platform.		
Social media mentions of platform*				
Blog posts/news articles that reference platform*				
Number of users*		One measure of impact is on https://github.com/cardat/ai-health-sws-r-targets where you can click on Star and Fork button. This shows that 1 user has taken 'Forked' copies of the codes for their work and also 1 user has 'Starred' the repo to be notified of updates. The more people who Star our repository the more impact we have.		
Number of active users (over 90-day period)				
Number of jobs run (i.e. number of processes submitted through the Platform)				
Instruments supported				
Number of engagement/outreach activities (e.g. seminars, presentations, demos, meetings with new stakeholders)*	15	9		
Number of researchers trained (online or face-to-face)*				

Availability of the platform (days in operation vs days offline)	NA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 100% access via GitHub to the R-targets repo. 2. Approx. 100% access to CoESRA VDI desktops. 3. 100% access to local compute on research desktops. 		
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15. Links to publications and other communications

Published datasets generated by platform

Date	Link to a metadata record <i>or</i> Citation with DOI
<i>Example:</i> 20/10/2021	https://researchdata.ands.org.au/parkes-observations-project-semester-2010aprs/445704
2022	Data for deaths (daily expected) by age, Sydney Australia 2006–2018 from AIHW and ABS data (DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/MZSWN) available on request.

Publications using data generated by platform

Date	Citation with DOI
<i>Example:</i> July 1999	N. Paskin, "Toward unique identifiers," in <i>Proceedings of the IEEE</i> , vol. 87, no. 7, July 1999. https://doi.org/10.1109/5.771073

2022	Mortality Burden of Heatwaves in Sydney, Australia Is Exacerbated by the Urban Heat Island and Climate Change: Can Tree Cover Help Mitigate the Health Impacts? <i>Atmosphere</i> . 2022; 13(5):714. https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13050714
2022	Hanigan, I.C.; Chaston, T.B. Climate Change, Drought and Rural Suicide in New South Wales, Australia: Future Impact Scenario Projections to 2099. <i>Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health</i> 2022, 19. In Press. DOI TBC

Publications that cite/reference the platform

Date	Citation with DOI
<i>Example:</i> July 1999	N. Paskin, "Toward unique identifiers," in <i>Proceedings of the IEEE</i> , vol. 87, no. 7, July 1999. https://doi.org/10.1109/5.771073

Social media mentions of the platform

Date	Link
<i>Example:</i> July 2020	https://twitter.com/AusBiocommons/status/1251724453173538817?s=20

Blog posts/news articles that reference the platform

Date	Link
<i>Example:</i> July 2020	https://twitter.com/AusBiocommons/status/1251724453173538817?s=20

16. Details on engagement, outreach and training activities

Activity	Activity description	No. of participants	Date of activity
1. Previously reported activities	Please see previous report on 15 events in 2021	Total of 105 participants across 15 events	May 31, 2021; June 24, 2021; July 8, 2021; July 12, 2021; July 15, 2021; July 15, 2021; July 15, 2021; July 19, 2021; July 27, 2021; July 28, 2021; September 3, 2021; September 16, 2021 ; September 23, 2021; September 23, 2021; October 26, 2021; December 8, 2021;
2. Explained R-targets versus AirFlow	PL059 AirHealth project catchup ivan.hanigan@curtin.edu.au Jonathan.smillie@ardc.edu.au Cassandra.yuen@sydney.edu.au	3	Tue Feb 15, 2022 12pm – 1pm

	Demonstrated the R-targets and AirFlow applications to ARDC expert.		
3.1 Use case meeting	<p>AIR/HEALTH Platforms demo</p> <p>Ivan Hanigan; Karthik Gopi; Cassandra Yuen; Geoffrey Morgan</p> <p>Demonstrated the R-targets application to domain science experts</p>	4	Tuesday, 15 March 2022 11:00 AM-12:00 PM
3.2 Use case meeting	R-targets was demonstrated to Joseph Van Buskirk of the Sydney Local Health District Public Health Observatory (domain science experts)	2	2022-04-01
4. Platform infrastructure	<p>Developing new Virtual Desktop Service hosted on Nectar optimised for Geospatial Air/Health research</p> <p>Ivan Hanigan; Gerhard Weis; Andy Botting, Siddeswara Guru</p> <p>Requested new virtual desktop for geospatial air-health disease risk mapping on the nectar research cloud.</p> <p>My quote has been published on ARDC website and had several hundred readers</p> <p>https://ardc.edu.au/news/new-virtual-desktop-service-launched/</p>	4	Friday, 27 May 2022 11:00 AM-12:00 PM

5. Software developer project team de-brief	<p>Finishing ASDAF bushfire smoke model / netCDF tools project</p> <p>Ivan Hanigan; Leigh Tyers; Foad Farivar; Calvin Pang; Miles Sowden; Matthias Liffers; Daniel Marrable</p> <p>Github repo called air bushfire smoke netcdf tool/ funded by CAR platforms ARDC</p>	7	Friday, 3 June 2022 3:30 PM-4:30 PM
6. Use case meeting	ARDC workshop: Integrated National air pollution and health data	10	June 9, 2022
7.SWS comparison	Other tool BenMap and R-targets was demonstrated to Mark Cepak from UTS masters of data science	3	2022-06-01
8. Platform infrastructure	<p>PostGIS server upgrade and backup automation</p> <p>Ivan Hanigan; Alvin Sebastian (UQ); Karthik Gopi</p>	3	Wednesday, 15 June 2022 1:15 PM-1:45 PM
9. Engagement and cross pollination with other ARDC projects	<p>Project demonstrated to Dr Timothy Brown (Innovation and Tech lead for another ARDC platform project = https://ardc.edu.au/project/australias-scalable-drone-cloud/)</p>	2	June 19, 2022

10. Future plans	Future plans are predominantly about supporting the ARDC PS022 Bridges Health Impact Assessment work but also include linking with Dr Tim Brown (ARDC drones platform), Miles McBain (R-targets developer), Neil Fann (US EPA BenMap developer), Muhammad Ali (ARDC data engineer) and Jonathan Smillie (ARDC tech expert) in next month or two to ensure continued developments and impact.	TBC	TBC
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17. Details on users of the platform

If possible, provide a brief breakdown of where these users come from; for example, which institutions the core user groups are from, or how many users from each of the following broad categories: .edu.au, .gov.au, .org.au, .edu (international academic institutions), .com (gmails etc.), other.

Organisation type	Number of users
.edu.au	
.gov.au	
.org.au	
.edu	
.com	
other	

18. Impact stories

Please detail any research impacts or highlights here. Other impacts could include outcomes of industry collaborations, platform community activities leading to new policy or practice, etc. Stories from users of the platform are particularly useful.

The scientific workflow system from the platforms project PL059 is ready for public use (available on GitHub and deployed on TERN CoESRA Virtual Desktops). It provides mediated access to exposure and health datasets that are otherwise difficult to obtain, and in some cases are not available without extensive permissions and ethics procedures and even considerable cost. These privileged datasets can be accessed by our computational tools without disclosure, making the data FAIR. Our stakeholder and partner engagements throughout the project period have informed the standardised HIA methods, which will provide compelling evidence of health impacts and benefits of public health and policy interventions that are directly relevant to their activities. We have coded modules that allow users to select affected areas and times, allowing the production of precise evidence for lobbying of government and industry groups. During this year, our stakeholders at EPA Vic have incorporated the SWS as a central part of their environmental health tracking network systems, through which they will build targeted information products for industry groups, such as the Department of Environment, Water, Land and Planning and the Victorian Department of Transport. These products will enable users to independently model the health impacts of their infrastructure and regulatory decisions, thus maximising the population health benefits of future policy decisions and their implementation.

Project lead Dr Ivan Hanigan was able to demonstrate the cutting edge application of data science using this work and was a Chief Investigator on the funding application to launch a national consortium called the Healthy Environments And Lives (HEAL) National Research Network, which received \$10M from the National Health and Medical Research Council (Grant No. 2008937). Dr Hanigan co-leads the Data and Decision Support Systems work package for HEAL and will further develop this SWS project in that context with a large number of science and policy stakeholders.